

**ΕΛΛΗΝΙΚΗ ΕΠΙΤΡΟΠΗ ΤΟΥ ΔΙΕΘΝΟΥΣ ΣΥΜΒΟΥΛΙΟΥ
ΜΕΓΑΛΩΝ ΗΛΕΚΤΡΙΚΩΝ ΔΙΚΤΥΩΝ**

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TSO/DSO COLLABORATION IN MARKET ENVIROMENT

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ABSTRACT

The increasing integration of the Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) requires a stronger coordination between System Operators (SOs) and possible other actors to ensure that they are optimally used. The CoordiNet project, funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 Programme, aims at investigating and proposing several coordination schemes between system operators for the procurement and activation of system services in the most reliable and efficient way. In order to examine the efficiency of the proposed coordination schemes and products, three demonstrations at large scale will be implemented, in cooperation with market participants. This paper presents the coordination schemes, the system services and the products that will be analysed in the Greek demo, as well as the first insights from the development of the demonstration plan.

KEYWORDS: TSO-DSO coordination, data exchange platform, system services, local market.

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ΠΕΡΙΒΑΛΛΟΝ ΑΓΟΡΑΣ**

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ΠΕΡΙΛΗΨΗ

Η συνεχώς αυξανόμενη διείσδυση των Μονάδων Διεσπαρμένη Παραγωγής απαιτεί ισχυρότερο συντονισμό μεταξύ των διαχειριστών συστημάτων και των υπόλοιπων φορέων προκειμένου να διασφαλιστεί η βέλτιστη χρήση αυτών. Το ερευνητικό πρόγραμμα CoordiNet, το οποίο χρηματοδοτείται από το πρόγραμμα Horizon 2020 της Ευρωπαϊκής Επιτροπής στοχεύει στην διερεύνηση και πρόταση διαφορετικών σχημάτων συντονισμού μεταξύ των διαχειριστών συστημάτων για την προμήθεια και την ενεργοποίηση των υπηρεσιών συστήματος με τον πιο αξιόπιστο και αποτελεσματικό τρόπο. Προκειμένου να εξεταστεί η αποτελεσματικότητα των προτεινόμενων συστημάτων συντονισμού και προϊόντων, θα πραγματοποιηθούν τρεις επιδείξεις μεγάλης κλίμακα, σε συνεργασία με τους συμμετέχοντες στην αγορά. Το παρόν άρθρο παρουσιάζει τα διάφορα συστήματα συντονισμού, τις υπηρεσίες συστήματος και τα προϊόντα που θα αναλυθούν στην ελληνική επίδειξη, καθώς και τις πρώτες εικόνες από την ανάπτυξη του σχεδίου επίδειξης.

ΛΕΞΕΙΣ ΚΛΕΙΔΙΑ: Συνεργασία διαχειριστών μεταφοράς και διανομής, πλατφόρμα ανταλλαγής πληροφοριών, υπηρεσίες συστήματος, τοπική αγορά.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the increasing integration of the Renewable Energy Resources (RES) during the last years, the last years, transmission and distribution systems across Europe are facing many challenges. The stochastic generation of RES has led to the increase of the required reserve for system services such as congestion management and voltage control. Traditionally, the reserve was provided by the conventional generators connected to the transmission system. Nowadays, the significant amount of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) that has been installed mainly in distribution system enables these resources to provide system services utilizing their flexibility. However, in order to enable the provision of system services from the DERs to the distribution and transmission systems, a better communication and coordination between System Operators (SOs), as well as new market models are required.

The CoordiNet project (<https://coordinet-project.eu/>) aims at investigating and proposing several coordination schemes between SOs for the procurement and activation of system services leveraging the flexibility of DERs in the most reliable and efficient way. The key objectives of CoordiNet are:

1. Demonstrating the potential of an extent coordination between Transmission System Operators (TSOs) and Distribution System Operators (DSOs) leading to a more economic, reliable and environmentally friendly electricity supply to consumers.
2. Defining one or more standardized products and their related attributes for each of the examined system services and testing several set of product attribute values, including the reservation and activation process for the use of the assets and finally the settlement process.
3. Specifying and developing a TSO-DSO-Consumers cooperation platform for exchanging data and facilitating coordination between them paving the way for the interoperable development of a pan-European market.

Ten demo activities are foreseen to be carried out in Greece, Spain and Sweden. In each demo activity, different coordination schemes and type of system services in different time frames as well as their associated products will be tested. In addition, the provision of flexibility by various types of DERs will be examined. In total seven coordination schemes proposing different solutions to different circumstances, and six system services have been identified. Each coordination scheme defines the roles of SOs and a high-level market design for the procurement of system services.

Focusing on the Greek demo, the objectives are to enable coordination and information exchange between TSO and DSO in order to improve efficiency of the system, prepare a consumer and RES to obtain a more active role in the management and operation of the power system in national and regional level and provide technological solutions allowing the creation of several new products and services. Two system services will be tested in two demonstration sites located at Kefalonia island and Mesogeia area. In particular, congestion management and voltage control will be examined ensuring the enhanced cooperation between TSO and DSO. Furthermore, two coordination schemes will be investigated. The application of a suitable coordination scheme between TSO and DSO and Flexibility Service Providers (FSPs) enables the creation of active local markets for gathering and trading flexibility of users connected to the distribution system and allows all market participants to provide system services and opens up new revenue streams for them.

This paper presents the coordination schemes as well as the system services and the products that will be analysed in the Greek demo and the first insights by the development of the demonstration plan.

2. COORDINATION SCHEMES, PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

As already mentioned, in order to enable the provision of system services from DERs new products and coordination schemes should be defined. This chapter presents the coordination schemes and products defined in WP1 of the CoordiNet project.

2.1. Coordination schemes

Building on the coordination schemes proposed by previous European projects and reviewing the relevant state-of-the-art literature review, seven groups of coordination possibilities emerged. The proposed coordination schemes can be applied for the provision of different system services or a combination of them.

Four classification layers were used resulting to the proposed coordination schemes. These layers are:

1. *Need for flexibility*: Which SO-need(s) will be addressed?
2. *Buyer*: Which stakeholder(s) buy(s) the flexibility to answer the considered need(s)?
3. *Number of markets*: How many markets are considered?
4. *Access to distributed resources*: Does the TSO have access to DERs?

Based on these layers, the coordination schemes presented in Table I were obtained.

Table I
Categorization structure of coordination schemes considered within the CoordiNet project.

	NEED Which SO-need(s) will be addressed?	BUYER Which stakeholder(s) buy(s) the flexibility to answer the considered need(s)?	# MARKETS How many markets are considered?	RESOURCES Does the TSO have access to DER?
Local Market Model	Local need	DSO	1	NA
Central Market Model	Central need	TSO	1	Yes or No
Common Market Model	Local and central need	DSO and TSO	1	Yes
Multi-level Market Model			> 1	Yes
Fragmented Market Model				No
Integrated Market Model		DSO, TSO and commercial parties	1	Yes
Distributed Market Model	Local need	Peers	≥ 1	NA
	Local and central need			

In the **Local Market Model** there is no interaction between system operators and the DERs connected to the distribution system are not able to provide system services to the TSO. This market model is implemented only when local needs exist.

Contrariwise, in the **Central Market Model**, it is assumed that the system services are solely procured to answer a central need for flexibility and only the TSO is the only buyer. The DSO has a passive role, without real involvement in the active procurement of flexibility, while The TSO may or may not have access to DERs connected to distribution system.

The central and local needs are combined in the **Common Market Model**. This market model addresses the local and central needs within one single market, enhancing the role of the DSO. The existence of only one market increases the liquidity. In this market model, resources are automatically shared. Due to the complexity introduced by optimizing simultaneously the provision of system services to the TSO and the DSO, the computational requirements are challenging. Furthermore, this market model requires the inclusion of geographical information in every bid submitted to the market.

Compared to the Common market model, in the **Integrated Market Model**, beyond the SOs, commercial market parties are allowed to buy flexibility.

Local and central markets coexist in the **Multi-level Market Model**. On the one hand, the different markets create the need for extensive communication between the central TSO market and the local DSO markets and lead to a lower level of market liquidity compared to the common and integrated market model. On the other hand, the local market allows the small scale DERs to enter the market.

The **Fragmented Market Model** considers different markets for the DSO and the TSO that are buyers in split markets. Compared to the Multi-level market model, in this model the TSO does not have direct access to the DERs. Consequently, there is no need for a very elaborate communication between the TSO and the DSO. However, the TSO can indirectly leverage the flexibility of DERs connected to the distribution system, by appropriately scheduling the interconnections with the DSO(s).

As a last type of market structure, one could consider the **Distributed Market Model** for addressing local or local and central needs. The peers are the sole buyers in the market. Depending on the SO needs, a distributed market can have one or more markets. The implementation of this market model requires a complete restructuring of current regulation and market set-up.

2.2. Products and services

The SOs can make use of system services in order to ensure the secure and reliable operation of transmission and distribution systems. System services are defined as "*services provided to DSOs and TSOs to keep the operation of the grid within acceptable limits for security of supply and are delivered mainly by third parties*" [1]. The system services considered in CoordiNet are 1) balancing, 2) congestion management, 3) voltage control, 4) inertial response, 5) black start and 6) controlled islanding.

For the procurement of the system services a market-based procedure for procuring products for system services is considered. Products can be categorized into standard and specific products. Standard products are defined as "*harmonized products for the exchange of system service(s) with common characteristics across Europe (i.e. shared by all TSOs or by all DSOs or by all TSOs and DSOs)*". Specific products are defined based on location-specific requirements and are used when standard products are not sufficient to ensure operational security and to efficiently deliver the service or if certain flexible resources cannot participate to the service through standard products.

Within CoordiNet, one or more standard products were defined for each system service, with some commonly defined attributes. It is noted that the product attributes are not defined beforehand, but ranges of values are proposed and the decision is left to the SOs procuring the product. The different product characteristics considered in CoordiNet are shown in Table II.

The first six characteristics are illustrated in Fig. 1, while Fig. 2 presents the products for the different system services defined in CoordiNet. More details on the products and system services can be found in the deliverable D1.3 of CoordiNet [2].

Table II
Definition of product characteristics

Characteristic	Definition
Preparation period	The period between the request by the SO and the start of the ramping period.
Ramping period	The period during which the input and/or output of power will be increased or decreased until the requested amount is reached.
Full activation time	The period between the activation request by the SO and the corresponding full delivery of the concerned product.
Minimum/maximum quantity	The power (or change in power) which is offered, and which will be reached at the end of the full activation time. The minimum quantity represents the minimum amount of power for one bid. The maximum quantity represents the maximum amount of power for one bid.
Minimum/maximum duration of delivery period	The minimum/maximum length of the period of delivery during which the service provider delivers the full requested change of power in-feed to, or the full requested change of withdrawals from the system.
Deactivation period	The period for ramping from full delivery to a set point, or from full withdrawal back to a set point.
Granularity	The smallest increment in volume of a bid.
Validity period	The period when the bid offered by the FSP can be activated, where all the characteristics of the product are respected. The validity period is defined by a start and end time ¹ .
Mode of activation	The mode of activation of bids, i.e. manual or automatic. Automatic activation is done automatically during the validity period (with little or no direct human control), whereas a manual activation is done at the request of the SO.
Availability price	Price for keeping the flexibility available (mostly expressed in € /MW/hour of availability)
Activation price	Price for the flexibility actually delivered (mostly expressed in € /MWh)
Divisibility	The possibility for a system operator to use only part of the bids offered by the service provider, either in terms of power activation or time duration. A distinction is made between divisible and indivisible bids.
Locational information included	This attribute determines whether certain locational information needs to be included in the bid (e.g. identification of Load Frequency Control (LFC) area, congested area...)
Recovery period	Minimum duration between the end of deactivation period and the following activation.
Aggregation allowed	This attribute determines whether a grouped offering of power by covering several units via an aggregator is allowed.
Symmetric/asymmetric product	This attribute determines whether only symmetric products or also asymmetric products are allowed. For a symmetric product upward regulation volume and downward regulation volume has to be equal.

¹ The validity period thus reflects the time period where the FSP could provide the product through its bid, and should therefore be at least the full delivery period of the bid.

1. Preparation period
2. Ramping period
3. Full activation time (FAT)
4. Min & max quantity
5. Min & max delivery period
6. Deactivation period

Figure 1. Set of product characteristics

Figure 2. Products for system services defined in CoordiNet

3. GREEK DEMO

Kefalonia island and Mesogeia area are the two demonstration sites of the Greek demo. The system services to be tested in the Greek demo are congestion management and voltage control under Multi-level and Fragmented market models. Based on the system services and coordination schemes that the Greek Demonstrator aims to test, four BUCs were created: GR-1a, GR-1b, GR-2a, and GR-2b [3]. Different time frames and products (capacity and energy) will be examined. Moreover, various types of DERs will participate in the demonstration, such as RES, storage devices, a small CHP and a number of consumers. The overview of the Greek demo ambition is presented in Fig 3.

Figure 3. Overview of the Greek demo ambition

For the implementation of the Greek demo, the key component that needs to be developed is the so-called CoordiNet platform. The scope of this platform is twofold. First, it incorporates the defined system services products and coordination schemes in order to enable the market(s) for the provision of system services. Secondly, it enables the communication between the different parties and especially between the SOs allowing the system integration and information exchange between the TSO and DSO operational technology and information technology systems [4]. The above objectives are achieved using an Enterprise Service Bus (ESB) approach, as presented in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. General framework of the CoordiNet platform

The top ESB, presented in Fig. 4, acts as communication channel between the SOs, while the bottom ESB is used for information exchange required for the implementation of the market. The connection to each ESB, and between both ESBs, is done via MQTT or REST API. Some of the functions to be performed by the platform are listed below:

- Data and information sharing from TSO and DSO.
- Gathering of flexibility needs from both TSO and DSO.
- Exchanging the flexibility of each potential FSP that can provide a specific service.
- Gathering of market bids.
- Performing market clearing functions.
- Communicating the market results.
- Submitting activation bids to service providers and grid operators.
- Performing the settlement process.

As shown in Fig.4 some of the additional tools that will be developed in the Greek demo are the RES and load forecasting tools and the aggregation tool. The forecasting tools will be used to detect potential congestions and voltage violations and to calculate the required flexibility for their eliminations, while aggregator tools will be used to aggregate the small DERs connected to the distribution system in order to enable their participation in the local market of the DSO and the central market of the TSO.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The increased penetration of the DERs and RES has led to the need to establish a better communication and coordination between the SOs in order to utilize their flexibility and operate the system in a reliable and efficient way. This paper presents the work that has been done to this direction during the first year of the CoordiNet project focusing in the Greek demo. Seven coordination schemes that define the roles and responsibilities of each SO, when procuring and using system services, are presented. In addition, different system services and products for procuring them are presented. Regarding the Greek demo, the general framework is illustrated and the basic functions of the CoordiNet platform are listed. In addition, some of the required tools for the implementation of the demo are presented.

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